

Appendix 1: The National COVID 19 pandemic policies and study periods

	Main actions	Dominant variant in the world
Study periods		
NPI	March 1, 2020; March 3, 2021	
NPIP1	<p>First outbreak phase: March 1, 2020, to April 17, 2020</p> <p>C8: Restrictions on international travel: countries classification according to their epidemic status and border closer.</p> <p>C8: Restrictions on international travel: Border closure</p> <p>C1: School closing</p> <p>C4: Restrictions on gathering size (cancelation events and close coffee shops and restaurants, prohibit collective prayers)</p> <p>C8: Stay-at-home requirements: general stay-at-home</p> <p>C7: Restrictions on internal movement: travel ban between governorates</p> <p>H1: Public information campaign</p> <p>H2: Testing policy: Self-isolation of new cases</p> <p>H2: Contact tracing</p> <p>H2: Testing policy: Isolation of suspected cases (Quarantine)</p>	
NPIP2	<p>Zero cases phase: April 18, 2020 to June 18, 2020</p> <p>C1: School closing</p> <p>C7: Restrictions on internal movement: Curfew (20h-6h)</p> <p>C8: Restrictions on international travel: countries classification according to their epidemic status</p> <p>C8: Stay-at-home requirements: work with 50% of the workforce. Online work if possible (C8: Stay-at-home requirements: general stay-at-home leaved at 05/05/2020)</p> <p>H1: Public information campaign</p> <p>H2: Testing policy: National isolation center of confirmed cases: mandatory</p> <p>H2: Testing policy: Isolation of suspected cases in national centers (Quarantine): mandatory</p> <p>H2: Contact tracing</p>	
NPIP3	<p>Mitigate strategy: June 19, 2020 to September 6, 2020</p> <p>C8: Restrictions on international travel: Border closure leaved: selective opening of borders with keep of testing policy and contact tracing.</p> <p>C8: Stay-at-home requirements: work with 50% of the workforce.</p>	Not Specified
NPIP4	<p>Stop and Go epidemic control (07/09/2020; 03/03/2021)</p> <p>C8: Restrictions on international travel: selective opening of borders with testing policy and contact tracing</p> <p>C1: School closing leaved on September 2020 replaced by health protocol for the school and university.</p> <p>C4: Restrictions on gathering size (events without exceeding 30 people and use of café and restaurant terraces, collective prayers not without exceeding 30 people)</p>	Alpha Variant
PIP	COVID 19 immunization: March 3, 2022; December 1, 2022	
PIP1	Targeted vaccination (population at high risk): March 3, 2022 to July 19, 2021	Delta Variant

	<p>Establishment of the EVAX platform. Eligible persons have been called to register and a phone invitation will be sent to them.</p> <p>People whose age is greater than or equal to 60 years; Health professionals; Essential service professionals; People under the age of 60 with well-defined pre-existing chronic diseases; Children under 18 and pregnant women were excluded from the vaccination target groups during P3a.</p>	
PIP2	<p>Mass vaccination: July 20, 2021 to December 1, 2021</p> <p>In addition to the vaccination carried out every day from 8 a.m. to 6 p.m. following to EVAX invitations, several open vaccination days were carried out on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. July 21 and 22 days for adults over 45. 2. August 8 for adults over 39 years. 3. August 15, 2021 for adults aged 18-39 year. 4. August 29, 2021 for adults aged over 39 and young people aged 15-17 years. 5. September 4, 2021 dedicated to arms carriers and citizens who received the first dose of vaccine on August 8, 2021. 6. September 14, 2021 for education training and kindergarten managers. 7. October 9, 2021 for pregnant women 8. October 25 to 29, 2021 in all courts of first instance. 9. November 21, 2021 for adults aged over 18 years. <p>Regulation of the vaccination pass for international travelers with testing policy.</p> <p>Regulation of the vaccination pass for national public and private places (structures and headquarters under the state, local authorities and authorities, companies and public establishments, educational and university establishments, vocational training establishments, crèches, kindergartens and kouttaps in the public and private sectors, social protection centers, public and private health structures for accompanying the sick or for visits, prisons, re-education centers for child offenders and custody centers for visits, cafes, restaurants and various categories of premises, tourist units and spaces open to the public, places and spaces reserved for leisure activities and parties, and for hosting fairs, conferences, artistic and scientific events, culture and sports as well as places of worship).</p> <p>Vaccination coverage of population who received at least one vaccine dose passed from 12.9% to 49.6%.</p>	Delta Variant
PIP3	<p>Boost immunization period: December 1, 2021 to March 3, 2022</p> <p>Vaccination pass for international travelers remain mandatory with testing policy. Positive cases enforced 5-day self-isolation.</p>	Omicron BA1; BA2
PIP4	<p>Reduction in PI and in NPI: March 3, 2022 to December 1, 2022</p> <p>Vaccination pass for international travelers without testing policy at February 26; 2022).</p> <p>Second dose of immunity boosting for subjects over 60 years old (April 15; 2022)</p> <p>At 01/12/2022: cancellation of the vaccination pass obligation for travelers; mask wearing for confirmed cases of COVID 19; continuation of immune-boosting vaccination for the elderly and patients with chronic disease.</p>	Omicron BA5

NPI: non-pharmaceutical interventions; NPIP: non-pharmaceutical interventions periods; PI: pharmaceutical interventions; PIP: pharmaceutical interventions periods